

APPENDIX J

Example of sequences of coded conversation

Table J.1:
Sequence 8

Sequence	Group	Student	Message	Code
8	1	System	Yellow must use their jumping ability in order to reach the next point	
8	1	S2	Hey yellow, you have to use your power!	Feedback: Ability
8	1	S1	I don't know which power, if I haven't got any power at all.	CPS: B3
8	1	S1	And what is my power?	CPS: B3
8	1	S3	Jumping high and running, it doesn't look like jumping high alone. You have to look at...	CPS: B3
8	1	S1	Now. Get turbo!	CPS: B3
8	1	S3	The S2 has to get up there, there and jump over there.	CPS: B3
8	1	S2	Hey S1, you have to jump there, and from there you have to go over there.	CPS: B3
8	1	S1	I can't, look...	CPS: C2
8	1	S1	Look... See	CPS: C2
8	1	S2	Oh I don't have super powers	SCP: A3
8	1	S1	Waja	CPS: A3
8	1	S3	Yes we have, but we have to recover energy....	CPS: B1
8	1	S1	I can't do anything, see S2, I can't do anything... now I can.	CPS: D2
8	1	S1	Oh I get it, you see that yellow thing, you have to shoot it.	CPS: D1
8	1	S2	There it is, you have to shoot it!	CPS: D2
8	1	S1	To the green, I got it	CPS: D1
8	1	S1	Go to	CPS: B3
8	1	S2	We have already shot it	CPS: D2
8	1	S1	No, green is also missing	CPS: D2
8	1	S2	I want to go up there	CPS: C3
8	1	S1	How can you not? jump!	CPS: C3
8	1	S3	That's where I got it	CPS: D2
8	1	S1	Did you shoot it?	CPS: D2
8	1	S3	Yes	CPS: D2
8	1	S1	Oh really?	CPS: D2
8	1	S2	Hey, don't leave me here alone!	CPS: D3
8	1	S1	But shoot it then!	CPS: C2
8	1	S1	What's wrong with you?	CPS: C3
8	1	S1	So shoot it	CPS: C2

Table J.2
Sequence 7

Group	Student	Message	Code
1	System	Yellow must use his special ability to reach the path over the fallen branch.	
1	S2	Yellow must use his special ability to reach the path over the fallen branch.	Feedback: Ability
1	S1	Which fallen branch? Which one?....	CPS: A1
1	S1	Aah I get it, I get it	CPS: B1
1	S1	No, I can't look.	CPS: B2
1	S2	You have to use your ability S1!	CPS: B3
1	S1	My disability?	CPS: A3
1	S2	ability	CPS: A3
1	S1	And what is my ability?	CPS: A3
1	S1	To go jumping for there poh!	CPS: A3
1	S3	Look S2 is up, S1 is up look	CPS: C2
1	S3	Reach the cube	CPS: C2
1	S3	The S1 passed	CPS: C2

Table J.3
Sequence 61

Group	Sequence	Student	Message	Code
5	61	System	Green and Yellow must activate the switch located at the bottom of the lake.	
5	61	S1	Green and Yellow must activate... Which one is green? Who is green?	Feedback: Action
5	61	S3	Which green?	CPS: A3
5	61	S1	It says green and yellow must activate the closed switch over the water...	CPS: A1
5	61	S3	Done, I've disappeared again	CPS: C1
5	61	S1	That's where it's at!	CPS: D2
5	61	S2	but the thing is gone	CPS: D2
5	61	S1	Yes, it left...	CPS: D2
5	61	S3	I've already passed, yes! Down to the water!	CPS: D3
5	61	S3	Yes! you have to go to these buttons, I don't know....	CPS: B2
5	61	S2	Oh I fell into the water...	CPS: C2
5	61	S1	There is something, there is something!	CPS: D2
5	61	S1	Ah we have to get the power out of it	CPS: D1
5	61	S3	I want to jump, I want to see what this is for	CPS: C1
5	61	S3	what happens if you activate the button?	CPS: C2
5	61	S1	I have already activated it...	CPS: C2
5	61	S2	I have already activated it	CPS: C2
5	61	S1	There it is, here it is, I can continue	CPS: C2
5	61	S3	No no no no, but S1	CPS: D3
5	61	S1	Why?	CPS: D3
5	61	S3	If you go through, we all have to go through, because it's closed.	CPS: D3

Table J.4
Sequence 21

Sequence	Group	Student	Message	Code
21	2	System	Green must go from the beginning of the level, to the tree at the small lake.	
21	2	S1	Why it says green should go from the start....	Feedback: Movement
21	2	S2	Because green is the most important	CPS: A3
21	2	S1	Who is green?	CPS: A3
21	2	S2	I don't know, I'm yellow, so I'm the green one.	CPS: A3
21	2	S1	S3 look look there's yours	CPS: A3
21	2	S3	Where?	CPS: A3
21	2	S1	Here the yellow	CPS: A3
21	2	S1	But how do I go to the start?	CPS: B2
21	2	S3	Back there...	CPS: B2
21	2	S1	Yes, but there is a limit, you see?	CPS: B2

Table J.5
Sequence 22

Group	Sequence	Student	Message	Code
2	22	System	Yellow must go to the top of the tree at the small lake.	
2	22	S2	Yellow should go on top of the small tree in the lake... of the small lake...	Feedback: Movement
2	22	S1	How do I get there?	CPS: B2
2	22	S2	... from the tree in the small lake.	CPS: B1
2	22	S1	I am going to test my power	CPS: B1
2	22	S2	Come on, come on! You have to go up, you have to go up!	CPS: D2
2	22	S1	No! Ah right S3 look!	CPS: B2
2	22	S2	You have to go up there, and go straight through	CPS: B2
2	22	S2	They have to continue...	CPS: B3
2	22	S1	Let's get our energy back please	CPS: B2

Table J.6
Sequence 48

Sequence	Group	Student	Message	Code
48	4	System	Make sure your colleagues arrive	
48	4	S2	Guys, I found a way through, hurry up!	Feedback: Status
48	4	S2	Hurry up, we can all go through there.	CPS: B3
48	4	S1	This way?	CPS: B1
48	4	S2	And he told me to make sure my colleagues arrive, so....	CPS: B1
48	4	S3	Use your shield	CPS: C1
48	4	S1	I don't have a shield, I just have strength.	CPS: C1
48	4	S2	And why don't the two of them pass together?	CPS: C1
48	4	S1	Let's see you come!	CPS: C1

Table J.7
Sequence 90

Sequence	Group	Student	Message	Code
90	7	System	I was hoping to see everyone here	
90	7	S1	They all have to get here	Feedback: Status
90	7	S1	S2, it looks like you have to go over there, and you don't have to jump in here.	CPS: C1
90	7	S2	Aah and the other one has to go over there, now.	CPS: C3
90	7	S1	And where do I stay?	CPS: C1
90	7	S3	What about me?	CPS: C1
90	7	S1	You have to go up, you don't have to go this way.	CPS: C1
90	7	S1	I follow you S2	CPS: C1
90	7	S2	Where did you go, downstairs?	CPS: C1
90	7	S1	Yes, underneath... S3 has to go straight down there it seems, see	CPS: C1
90	7	S3	To where?	CPS: C1
90	7	S1	To the top	CPS: C2
90	7	S1	S2 you don't have to go this way, you have to go down.	CPS: C1
90	7	S2	Aaah right...	SCP: A1
90	7	S3	Look, I went into a tunnel.	CPS: D1
90	7	S1	No S3, you have to go up.	CPS: C1
90	7	S1	Look there he comes out, Red... Aah I have to go this way	CPS: C1
90	7	S1	Like S2, that's your way... I have to go upstairs.	CPS: C1

Table J.8
Sequence 81

Sequence	Group	Student	Message	Code
81	7	System	Is everyone here already?	
81	7	S1	Is everyone here already?	Feedback: Status
81	7	S1	Oh we must all be here	CPS: B3
81	7	S1	S2 we all have to be here, I'm already here.	CPS: B3
81	7	S1	S2, we must all be here, look!	CPS: B3
81	7	S2	Ah ok, wait for me	CPS: B3
81	7	S1	... or do I have to go straight on? no, I have to wait for them.	CPS: B3
81	7	S3	Look I showed up there now...	CPS: D3
81	7	S1	Everybody has to be here where I am, have you arrived?	CPS: D3
81	7	S3	I'm coming, I'm in the woods	CPS: C3
81	7	S1	Ah, we're all together now, only the S2 is missing.	CPS: C3
81	7	S1	S2 you are missing	CPS: C3
81	7	S2	I am now with "kayoken".... I am now with "kayoken"	CPS: B2
81	7	S1	S2 you are missing	CPS: D2
81	7	S2	Already, to the shot	CPS: C3

81	7	S3	I have arrived	CPS: C3
81	7	S2	Ya, I'm reloading "kayoken"	CPS: C3
81	7	S3	How much time do you have left S2?	CPS: C3
81	7	S1	We are waiting for you S2	CPS: C3
81	7	S1	Ah, you're here?	CPS: D3
81	7	S3	You have to go straight ahead	CPS: D3
81	7	S1	Yes, straight ahead... After you disappear and you show up here and we're all back together again.	CPS: D3
81	7	S3	You're almost there, then you have to go into a cave and there are some buttons.	CPS: D3
81	7	S2	Here I am	CPS: D3
81	7	S1	You're here!	CPS: D3
